

NDONGENGI : A SOLUTION TO OVERCOME VALUE-SHIFTING AS AN IMPACT OF THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION 4.0 IN INDONESIA

Zahro'ul Aini¹, Nur Lailiya Hartanti², Norasiah³

1. Universitas Negeri Malang

2. Universitas Airlangga

3. UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang

zahroaini82@gmail.com

Abstract

The industrial revolution 4.0 is a term to describe the awakening of the fourth industrial revolution, i.e. a transformation to improve the efficiency of work integrated with digital capabilities. Industry 4.0 does indeed offer a plethora of benefits, but obstacles are also present to be overcome. Drath and Horch (2014) argued that the challenges faced by a country when implementing industry 4.0 is the emergence of resistance to changes; such as demographic & social aspects shifts, instability of political conditions, resources limitedness, the risk of natural disasters, and the demands of environmentally friendly technologies' applications. One example of social change that will impact Indonesia is individualistic attitude tendency that would later cause the lack of social sensitivity within the community—meanwhile, values such as *gotong-royong* (mutual cooperation), friendliness, and togetherness are all Indonesia's identity as a nation. In other words, , Indonesia needs a solution to mold the youth to be ready to play a role in industrial advancement all while possessing high moral standard through early educations by means of local wisdom-based storytelling. It is considered an effective method to cultivate the moral values of life. This study aims to derive an analysis of the basic concepts of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 on the lives of Indonesian society and offer a local wisdom-based storytelling solution. This study uses an ex-post facto methodology as the methods of analysis together with literature study to deepen the analysis of the research. The result of this study are utilized to address the negative impact of the industrial revolution 4.0.

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1. Introduction

Revolution, in Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI), means alteration which has characteristic very fast , while understanding of industrial is the effort in doing production process. When that two words are combined, they have meaning the alteration in production process quickly. This rapid change does not only mean increasing the quantity of goods produced (quantity), but also improving the quality of production (quality).The term "Industrial Revolution" was popularized by Friedrich Engels and Louis-Auguste Blanqui in 19th century Zhejiang. This industrial revolution is currently running from time to time. The current decade can be used in the fourth phase 4.0. Change the phase to the phase of giving an articulate number on the side of its use. The first phase (industrial revolution 1.0) fought on the discovery of machines that stressed the mechanization of production. The second phase (industrial revolution 2.0) has moved to mass production stages that are connected with quality control and standardization. The third phase (industrial revolution 3.0) allows the stage of uniformity. The

fourth phase (4.0 industrial revolution) has presented digitalization and automation of the integration of the internet with manufacturing.[1]

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 era (hereinafter: Era 4.0) has no simple impact. It affects all aspects of human life. Included this problem, that is the national moral and character. Until the term "education 4.0" emerged (Education 4.0) which is a term by educational experts to describe various ways to integrate cyber technology both physically and unintentionally into the educational process. Children's education in particular now inevitably has to keep abreast of the flow of digitalisation, such as the use of gadgets and other technologies in providing learning to children. It has positive and negative impacts.

Gadgets certainly have a myriad of advantages to facilitate human life in the current era, from service providers to applications supporting daily activities. But the continued use of gadgets will also adversely affect patterns of human behavior, especially for children, in their daily life, those who tend to constantly use gadgets will be very dependent and become activities that must and routinely be carried out by children in their daily activities, no doubt at this time children play gadgets more often than learn and interact with the surrounding environment. This is worrying, because in childhood they were still unstable, had a very high curiosity, and influenced the increasing consumptive nature of children for the use of gadgets in children need to get special attention for parents. Some cases regarding the negative impact of this smartphone often afflict children. Starting from internet addiction, games, and also content that contains pornography. [2]

The value shifting above is one of the impacts of Era 4.0. Responding to this, it is necessary to promote the planting of the moral values and character of the Indonesian people to Indonesian children as early as possible. One of them is through storytelling activities. Storytelling is an effort carried out by storytellers in conveying the contents of the meeting, thoughts or a story to children verbally containing moral messages. [3] Storytelling is considered effective as a form of media for cultivating values and characters for children. That moral value will later become a fortress and provision for Indonesia's young generation in the face of the 4.0 Industrial Revolution whose impact is increasingly evident.

2. Research Methods

This research is an ex-postfacto research form. Ex-postfacto type chooses information to get the data which has been done by tracing backwards to find out the factors that can cause these events without giving effect to the subject under study. [4] This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach. Qualitative research method is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism, which used to find natural objects, (as opposed to experimentation) where researchers are as key instruments. [5] The implementation of qualitative description analysis is carried out by taking data from research subjects, informations, restoration data and information, data and information of research subjects, and falsifying the results of the description. Direct communication, and fact-finding to strengthen the thoughts that will be presented. This method is used to determine the level of morality in everyday life.

3. Result and Discussion

As developing era, challenges and obstacles in instilling moral values to the young generation of the nation's successors also continue to experience development and change. If over the past few decades, close conversations between children and parents are close family ties, today is a rare thing. Children are more comfortable with gadgets and other technologies.

This certainly creates a paradigm shift in terms of looking at the moral values of the nation's children, considering that they are the next generation.

The shift and change as little described above is an inevitable necessity. This is due from time to time human demands and needs continue to experience change. Today, broad knowledge alone cannot guarantee a graduate can speak much in global competition. Specific expertise is also needed that is in line with the needs of the field. If this is not the case, then education graduates will be crushed and excluded. Moreover, the world has entered a new era, namely the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0. But unfortunately, this makes our children become self-oriented and individualistic individuals. This attitude is actually not the original character of the Indonesian people who are famous for mutual cooperation with Indonesian eastern culture.

Indonesia is known as a culture-rich country, as a manifestation of the diversity of tribes inhabiting the islands of Sumatra to Papua. Culture as a pattern of life is comprehensive, complex, abstract, and broad, and is a determinant of communicative behavior embedded in various human social activities. [6] As a civilized nation, Indonesia upholds the nature of culture as an order of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, and meanings [7], which among them are correlated with one another as one-on-one. Public awareness of the nature of culture, especially values and attitudes, encourages a harmonious life. This introduces Indonesia as a country that adheres to the "eastern" values that uphold tolerance, courtesy, gentleness, and mutual help so as to provide a picture of good values for the younger generation. [8]

Indonesia has a powerful of speech culture since the grandmother is a storytelling that also acts as a local wisdom. Storytelling or commonly called storytelling is a method of communication for children that turns out to be more effective (Ibnoe, 1999). The effectiveness of storytelling can be used as a means of delivering messages about something. The narrator has a specific purpose towards the listener about the story being told. Likewise in storytelling. [3] While according to Pellowski (1977) defines storytelling as an art or art from a narrative skill from stories in poetry or prose, which are shown or led by one person in front of the audience directly where the story can be narrated by telling or sung, with or without music, images or other accompaniment that may be learned orally, either through printed sources, or through mechanical recording sources (Boltman, 2001).

Storytelling can be done since the child is in the womb. Or since the age of 0 (baby) and the age of children. According to WHO criteria, the category of children is from ages 0 to less than 18 years. Storytelling indirectly answers the needs of children in imagination. Imagination answers children's curiosity. His brain is in need of it (Chatib, 2016: 24) When we tell stories the child will imagine whatever we tell. The age at which children are very effective for imagining is usually the age of a toddler. While in elementary school age, the element of imagination in children is mixed with the level of the ability of the brain to analyze a story. So the story and how to tell stories must be adjusted.[12]

According to Josette Frank quoted by Asfandiyar (2007), like adults, children get emotional release through fictitious experiences that they have never experienced in real life. Fairy tales turned out to be an effective way to develop cognitive aspects (knowledge), affective (feelings), social, and conative aspects (appreciation) in children.

Storytelling techniques and selection of good story materials must begin to be studied so that children are able to understand the information conveyed maximally. In the modeling theory proposed by Albert Bandura human cognitive stages there are several stages, namely attention, remembering, motion reproduction and motivation. Storytelling will be successful when the child can focus on paying attention to the contents of the story and get to know the characters who are told, then the children will remember the contents of the story and stored in

the memory of the brain, which can be retrieved whenever needed, after which the children will translate the memory of the story that is in his brain in the form of behavior in which this behavior is based on self-motivation which is also obtained from the story of the story conveyed. [9] The criteria for good storytelling according to Elis from the Indonesian Gendong community is when storytellers can become the children. Not as an adult who patronizes and advises. [12]

The term *Ndongengi* is taken from Javanese vocabulary which has the same meaning as storytelling. This concept must have a reason, the concept of *ndongengi* in this problem is storytelling as from the tradition of the Indonesian people. Traditions that have existed since ancient times that have begun to fade. Where storytelling at that time was closely related to folklore stories that developed. according to Brunvand (Asis, 2015: 154-155) explained that fairy tales are the part of folklore and folklore itself is part of oral folklore. Examples are satria stories, the hero has good moral values and commendable behavior that children can think and imagine that he must be able to become that figure, so he knows he must be the protagonist in the story that is told.

The strength of the local fairy tale is loaded with the teachings of the values of local wisdom which are considered ancient and have no relevance to progress, so that the values contained in local wisdom are forgotten. Though these values provide signs so that they become polite, wise, and wise individuals in responding to life. These values are widely found in the local fables of the archipelago, including in the heroic stories of Nusantara history and bedtime stories (Sarumpaet, 1976; Salamah, 2012). [10] The adoption of the concept of *ndongengi* will be integrated with the concept of digitalization in which we cannot separate the millennial era from the progress.

In the research by McClelland that discovered there were certain nations whose people worked hard to advance and others did not. He compared English and Spanish. In the 16th century, the two countries were two giant wealthy countries. However, Britain continued to grow into bigger, while Spain declined to become a weak country. After being researched, McClelland discovered stories and stories of children who were different from the two countries. In the UK, children's tales contain a kind of "virus" that causes readers to be infected with the disease need to be accomplished', the need for achievement, while the stories in Spain actually lull and do not contain the "virus" (McClelland, 1976; Salamah, 2012). [11]

Exposure to globalization as an effect of the 4.0 Industrial Revolution, one of which is that children are easy to watch shows that are not right for their age. Whether it's through television or the internet. To overcome this, fairy tales can be applied by following the digitization flow. Like the *dongeng.tv* site which is a collaboration of the Storytelling Movement of Indonesia (Gendong) and the Young Indonesia Forum (FIM) is one form of effort so that the fairy tale about the values commended in the digital world compensates for the other adverse effects. Children actually have the value of being entrusted by God, but we as adults are responsible for growing those values before eroded by bad values due to the times. Fairytale source sites are very helpful for parents / adults in getting inspired fairy tales for children.

In Indonesia, storytelling activities have begun to develop a lot, even becoming a number of community associations, libraries, bookstores and reading parks that hold storytelling activities regularly as their agenda. One of the case studies conducted by Elis was a routine storytelling activity during the month of Ramadan in 2011 in the Ciparai area. With the background of quiet children, Ciparai children lack motivation to aspire to high aspirations because of lack of encouragement from family and the environment.

Figure 1. The concept of ndongengi as a solution to industrial revolution 4.0

When the impact of digitization comes on them, they turn into rebels with the desire that their ideals will be supported, but because there is no assistance in resolving conflicts within themselves and the environment around Ciparai, assessing children when they finish high school will work as factory workers, as happened in industrial centers in Indonesia. There is their desire to aspire, but the value that reaches them is the value of rebellion. But after the storytelling comes, they become focused and understand which values they should develop and which they should avoid. Ciparai children have been able to express their aspirations in detail after storytelling activities.

Another case study came from Gadang, Malang. In 2014 Malang's fairy tale community together with the child social welfare agency provided assistance once a week. From the initial conditions of the Gadang children who were like thugs and arrogant, became calm and wiser in making friends. The first big kids bother the little ones, become caring for you and protect each other when playing.

The storytelling method is also different from the others, the application of which is to compile structured stories with figures close to the Gadang children, insert good values and tell them stories. Not to say "don't fight" or "don't hit" but rather to tell that one of the characters when hit will feel sick, then the hiter gets a hit and turns out to be sick, and finally concludes that being beaten is sick, don't hit because of hurting others .

Storytelling will be effective when massively applied by parents, schools and adults to Indonesian children. With capital, the increasing number of storytelling communities in Indonesia which are spread in various regions, will further encourage Indonesia to become a nation with civilized society, not easy to compete and wise because from the beginning instilled values of goodness.

The big storytelling community includes Ayo Dongeng Indonesia, Kampung Dongeng, Rumah Dongeng Mentari, Gerakan Mendongeng Indonesia (Gendong), and many more. The role of the youth and government community is also needed to collaborate in fostering parents and inviting adults to establish the values of typical Indonesian goodness for children in an effort to prevent and overcome the negative effects of changes in the paradigm of moral values due to the digitalization of the industrial revolution 4.0.

4. Conclusion

The developing of digitalization by industrial revolution 4.0 forces Indonesia to be truly prepared to face the good and bad effects that accompany it. Social problems will become very serious when not well anticipated as early as possible. The negative impact of Era 4.0 in the social life of Indonesian children is getting more and more real. Indonesian children are driven to be individualistic and lack empathy for others, and increasingly dependent on the presence of gadgets with various features and wide access. Changes in the moral values of Indonesian children now compared to before are so far away with the digitization in all sectors

of life. The initial and fundamental steps that are considered effective, one of which is to tell stories of the values of Indonesian local wisdom that can shape the personality of Indonesian children who are good, wise, empathetic, and other good attitudes as early as possible. This step is a preventive step to prevent adverse effects Era 4.0 is getting bigger in Indonesia in the future. Also as a step to overcome the adverse effects that have begun to be felt now, parents / adults can "cheer up" children about stories that can indoctrinate them into Indonesian personalities in the face of Era 4.0.

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